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Implementation of 3D Simulation to Foster Digital Twin Based Applications in Manufacturing: An Educational Case Study

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Abstract

Digitalization is a worldwide trend spreading across several industrial sectors, such as production, logistics or planning. Due to the increasing complexity of industrial settings and manufacturing systems, emerging technologies allowing digitalization are crucial for the development and affirmation of the digital transformation to its fullest. This is indeed made possible by the use of various digital tools, available to industries as well as to the scientific community. Digital transformation driven by digital technologies, such as virtual/augmented reality, 3D simulation, cloud computing and Digital Twins, has been of great interest for practitioners from industries and for research institutions. The introduction of radical changes in industry creates the need to also train future engineers who are going to enforce the digital transformation process. The proposed study aims to contribute to the demonstration of the efficacy and potential of the implementation of a Digital Twin based on real-time data collection and 3D simulation with an intelligent mechatronic transfer system as practical use case. The result of this work is the creation of a demonstrator about 3D simulation in Digital Twin-based applications in manufacturing; purpose of it is that students and practitioners from industry can self-replicate during lab experiences and trainings in a learning factory environment.

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1. Introduction

The manufacturing sector has currently faced a period of change over the last years, due to the request in high variability of products and the increasing complexity of manufacturing systems [1]. Changes related to the product integration phases over their overall lifecycle have however been growing together with a more common employment of digital technologies, which are crucial to guarantee the building of an up-to-date digital layout of a manufacturing system [2]. The transformation towards this kind of manufacturing, commonly referred to as smart manufacturing [3], is indeed one of the hottest trends nowadays. One such technology, rapidly spreading and being exploited for implementation cases in smart manufacturing systems, is the so-called Digital Twin (DT), which represents a link between the real and the digital world [4]. Thanks to the development of a DT, the provision of updates about the status of a manufacturing system but also its real-time optimization can be facilitated and expedited. Together with the diffusion of DT instruments, a common need for an appropriate training and education about related concepts is becoming a must not only for experts in the field, but also for students and practitioners at an undergraduate and graduate level [5]. It is indeed of great importance that students, who could be future researchers, practitioners, or company experts, are well trained in the implementation, use and advantages of the DT concept. To do so, appropriate environments, in which both theoretical and practical knowledge could be shared, might be Learning Factories [6]. They constitute indeed well-established communities for research, technology demonstration and education, frequently bridging together the industry and research world to produce and transfer knowledge [6].

Scope of the proposed study is to contribute to the spread of DT education in a Learning Factory context. This work describes the realization of a use case involving digital modelling and simulation of an intelligent mechatronic transfer system with the utilization of a 3D simulation software for educational purposes. Aims of this paper are the correct set-up of the simulation environment, reflecting all the functions available in the real-life system, achieving a DT configuration; the implementation of a use case that can be used for educational purposes, for training both undergraduate and graduate students as well as practitioners from industry. In this sense, the use case must not be complex to understand, yet must feature all the fundamental concepts regarding 3D-simulation in DT-based applications, such as flexibility, interoperability, resilience and automatic data flow [7]. Students and practitioners will indeed have the possibility to self-develop specific components of the demonstrator in occasion of field-oriented lectures at university, gathering detailed knowledge about DT related concepts with a learning-by-doing teaching format.

To conclude, the paper is structured as follows: first, a brief state of the art about DT technology in engineering education and Learning Factories is reported in Section 2. Thereafter, the experimental methodology and the implementation and testing phases are presented, respectively, in Section 3 and 4, together with the key results of the designed DT use case. Finally, conclusions and future work are drawn.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1. Digital Twin Technology in Engineering Education

With the current trend of a continuous growth in digitalization, technologies enabling the digital transformation constitute a hot topic for the whole scientific community [8]. There are numerous tools and methods to achieve the digitalization goals, among which the will to integrate physical systems into the digital world with a continuous exchange of data sets has nowadays a huge importance. Hence, the implementation of the concept of Digital Twin lies in a focal point [9]. With DT, the scholars refer to an exact copy of a physical system or object, automatically transferring information to its virtual twin and vice versa. This results in a fully integrated physical and virtual model, where any change in the physical world occurs also in the digital one and vice versa [10].

Together with the increasing popularity of DT, it becomes however crucial the need for training in the application of this technology. The development of appropriate digital competences in the field can be for sure helpful for researchers but also practitioners [11]; from the point of view of researchers, such skills can impact on the quality of scientific dissemination and are also beneficial for maintaining an up-to-date knowledge about the topic [5]. Moreover, training practitioners to gain experience in highly digitalized workspace can be addressed as an added value by companies, which desire to remain competitive with the digitalization of their environments [12]. Consequently, it is clear that education, specifically in the engineering field, should update from traditional methods, so that students, which could be future researchers or practitioners, can benefit from concepts but also practical use cases on the topic of DT [5]. To this regard, some examples of development of DT training tools are present in literature, such as the ones in [8-9], where scholars present the realization of a complete DT driven to educational usage. In [13], a practical simulation-driven case study is used to foster DT knowledge throughout an MSc level course. Another example is reported by [14], which deals with the capacity of virtual technologies for education: in this contribution, the usefulness of novel technologies (such as DT and virtual reality) for students' education is demonstrated via a web-based virtual gaming. To conclude, there could be challenges and difficulties in focusing educational purposes on this topic, as highlighted by [8], for instance potential misinformation about the concept and definition of DT but also a scarce availability of digital tools in university or lab facilities. Nevertheless, the tendency to transfer knowledge about the benefits of DT through virtual or physical demonstrating platforms is still growing.

2.2. Digital Twin and Learning Factories

Along with the increase in digitalization and the dissemination of concepts related to the new industrial revolution, the birth and diffusion of Learning Factories have increased in the last years. Learning Factories represent indeed essential infrastructures, where the real digital transformation can occur and be transmitted on an educational level [6]. Despite the recurring challenges for building a complete Learning Factory, such as lack of appropriate facilities or limited budget, these structures have the possibility to become a meeting point for students, researchers, practitioners, teachers, and professionals, who share the common goal of enhancing the transfer of knowledge, specifically regarding digital technologies [15]. Focusing on DT, Learning Factories may represent a suitable environment to foster knowledge about its potentialities and benefits, for instance thanks to the development of DT demonstrators, which can be utilized for educational purposes. A practical and relevant example is described by scholars in [16]: their main scope was the set-up of an educational turbocharger prototype

and the creation of its DT, deployed at the Aalto Factory of the Future (AFoF) learning factory. This resulted in a complete demonstrator, made of a communicating physical object and digital platform, with the aim of training students in DT concepts. A similar study was conducted by [17], in which the DT of a physical system for a Changeable Learning Factory (CLF) was developed. A crucial point highlighted by the scholars is that such use cases and hands-on experiences can be extremely beneficial for the acquisition of digital competences specifically on the topic of DT, due to their practice-oriented aspects. These indeed attract students more and can be also more understandable with respect to frontal or theoretical explanation about DT [16]. This is the reason why Learning Factories workspaces are nowadays becoming the hub where digitalization on an educational level can occur in the most effective way.

3. Research Objectives and Methodology

In this section, the authors aim at analyzing the founding research objectives (RO), together with the methodology followed to reach them. As already described in the previous section, the need to establish practical demonstrators capable of supporting theoretical lectures about the DT paradigm in Learning Factories, is of crucial importance as the digitalization processes in industrial settings require highly specialized workforce and knowledgeable experts in Information Technology-related topics, such as IoT, communication protocols, network infrastructures, and cybersecurity [18]. For these reasons, the research objectives posed in this work are the following:

- Design an industrial-like case-study that highlights the benefits of 3D simulation in DT applications (RO-1).
- Implement the designed case-study mentioned in RO-1 as a real-life scenario (RO-2).

A case-study has been developed at the Smart Mini Factory laboratory of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano. As per definition, the main characteristic of a DT application is the complete integration of the physical world and the virtual one, meaning that the data collection processes, as well as the optimization procedures are carried out autonomously, without the need of further decision-making processes, nor manual data transportation [10]. To embody this view of a DT application, the conceptual design and data flow has been structured as following. The conceptual structure encompasses a DT application layer, which oversees collecting information from the physical environment and dispatching tasks, following manufacturing rules and constraints. Collected information are stored in an open database, accessible by virtual and physical actors of the system. The peculiarity of the designed system lies in the fact that tasks are not only dispatched to the physical environment but are simultaneously shared with the virtual replica of the physical environment. Since the virtual environment is modelled in such a way to accurately reflect the behavior of the real one, tasks dispatched to the virtual world are carried out, applying provisional modifications to the manufacturing parameters, allowing the DT layer to “explore” different ways in which the dispatched task could be performed, thanks to the 3D simulation module. In this configuration, the tasks that have been dispatched to the physical world will be performed, while simulation runs will look for possible improvement. Given the data collected in the real world and the ones produced during the simulation runs, the DT layer will be able to dispatch improved tasks.

After the conceptual design has been completed, it has been implemented in a real-life application, in which physical entities are put into communication with virtual entities and the data exchange happens as described above. Details about the implementation are provided in the next section.

4. Implementation and Testing

The purpose of this section is to describe in detail the practical case-study developed for this work, in particular the physical architecture of the demonstrator in exam and the implementation of the DT application. First of all, the physical system chosen for pursuing the scopes of this research is a flexible and intelligent transfer line, brand Montrac®, that is currently present at the Smart Mini Factory laboratory of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano. The transfer line is composed of two main rail-loops, seven workstations, two switches and three shuttles. These components are thought to serve as transportation mean in a future DT-based assembly line. Along the transfer line, two robotic manipulators are currently present, represented by a 4-arm traditional robot (Adept Omron 4) and by a 6-joints collaborative robotic arm (Universal Robot UR10) equipped with a gripper. The configuration of the transfer line at the laboratory is partially depicted in Figure 1, where the two switches are shown in the foreground, connecting the central and bigger rail-loop with the secondary one. The collaborative robotic manipulator UR10 is placed inside the main rail-loop, serving two mirrored workstations and a warehouse, which is at disposal of the traditional robot Omron 4, as well as a further workstation beneath it.

Fig. 1. Configuration of the assembly transfer line (physical)

In order to properly model the DT application explained above, the first step involved the creation of the virtual environment strictly mirroring all the elements characterizing the physical one. To do so, a 3D simulation software named iPhysics [19] has been exploited: starting from the 3D CAD model of the transfer line, the scholars imported all the required elements to create a copy of the physical mechatronic system into the virtual world. The outcome is presented in Figure 2.

A further step for the creation of the DT layer involved the replication of the movement control logic of the three shuttles along the rail paths of the transfer line. It needs to be specified that the control software made available from the supplier of the transfer line has not been purchased, therefore the software enabling the control logic of the transfer line has been developed from scratch. The result of the software development process enabled the seamless integration of the transfer line into connected environments. This provided the scholars with a significant freedom in the design of the overall control architecture and functioning purposes of the transfer line. In addition, this made possible the utilization of the control logic in the simulation software iPhysics. A peculiar script language is available in iPhysics and thanks to the possibility to model scripts and assign them to different components of the simulation, it was possible to seamlessly control the movement of shuttles. In particular, what occurs in the physical system has been replicated, i.e., the shuttle movement from one workstation to the subsequent one controlled by an input command provided by a potential user. In iPhysics, it is indeed possible to control the actual positioning of the shuttles by means of a parametrized function, knowing specifically on which part of the rail track each shuttle is at any instant in time. Moreover, the functioning of the track switches has been included in the simulation too; it needs to be specified that switches operate so that shuttles may follow by default the shortest path to reach a given workstation in the main loop, if not differently instructed.

The completion of the 3D simulation allowed scholars to obtain an exact copy of the real-world behavior of the transfer line also in the virtual world. At this stage, the correct set-up of the simulation environment, reflecting all the functions available in the real-life system, has led to the creation of a full virtual model encompassing physical as well as behavioural characteristics of the real-world transfer line application. This has been achieved by taking into consideration the educational purpose, which is lying behind. For this reason, the whole system (physical and digital) becomes easy to explain and to be understood in its entirety.

Fig. 2. Configuration of the assembly transfer line (virtual)

Recalling the data flow explained in Section 3, one can understand how the two worlds communicate with each other. In this peculiar application, the DT layer is in charge of triggering the same task (with specific parameters) both in the real world and in the virtual one. By doing so, the required task is immediately executed in the physical world, and its execution parameters are inherited by the previous simulation round. This leads to faster task dispatching, if assuming that the production parameters calculated for a previous similar task will still be acceptable. In the meanwhile, the same task is dispatched to the virtual replica of the physical system. Here several simulation runs are triggered simultaneously, and each simulation run aims at exploring different future scenarios, by slightly modifying the production parameters. By analysing the performance achieved in the simulation runs, the DT layer is then in charge of updating the effective production parameters to execute the upcoming tasks with the currently optimal parameters being set in the physical world.

The simulation-actuation procedure always happens simultaneously with the physical execution of the production processes. Hereby, the scientific definition of a DT application is reflected since the data collection procedure as well as the self-optimization features have been integrated and automatized.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

This work presented how the introduction of 3D simulation in DT application to foster systems self-optimization could be exploited to transfer knowledge from the academic environment to graduate and undergraduate students, as well as to practitioners from industry. The development of the described case study led the Smart Mini Factory of the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano to be able to offer a state-of-the-art industrial setup that serves as multifunctional teaching platform. The fulfillment of RO-1 provided the scholars with the design of the demonstrator in exam, that will serve for frontal lectures in university courses; the accomplishment of RO-2 resulted in the creation of the physical lab demonstrator, which students and practitioners will exploit and eventually advance in hands-on practice sessions. The modularity of the application described in this work makes it possible to split a modern DT application in its fundamental components, and treat them, as a whole, as functional groups, or as single entities, depending on the requirements of the training and courses taught. This approach enables fast reconfigurability of the physical and software architecture, to address scholars' needs. The modules that can be taught and demonstrated to students and practitioners from industry are dealing with 3D simulation methods, IoT, and retrofitting of legacy machines. In this configuration, it is also possible to practically re-develop each single component in hands-on courses, where attendees can learn-by-doing the concepts that would otherwise be only studied in frontal lectures.

In the future, the presented concepts might be extended in two main directions. 1) An improvement in the simulation capabilities of the software could extend the capabilities of the whole system. A possible and desirable path to be followed could be to implement machine learning techniques, in order to enhance the strength of this DT-based case study both from a practical and a didactical point of view. These would allow the 3D simulator to virtually evolve towards a general optimal configuration, by emulating the theory of the evolution of the species. 2) The physical structure of the case study can be extended to include more machines and software services. In this scenario, the data flow designed in Fig. 1 should not be affected, since the modularity of the systems prevents

it to be modified whenever the system is scaled or modified. From a technical perspective, the software components must undergo a rigorous round of testing and revision, to ensure robustness and maintainability.

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